

Influence of Extraction Methods on Antiplasmodial Potential of Bioactive Extracts from *Artemisia annua* L: Response Surface Methodology Approach for Microwave-Assisted Extraction

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ABSTRACT:

This study focuses the eco-friendly extraction of medicinal plants and the optimal conditions for extracting bioactive ingredients from *Artemisia annua* L., which is regarded as a rich source of secondary metabolites with antiplasmodial potentials. The research specifically aimed to optimize the microwave-assisted extraction method for secondary metabolites from *Artemisia annua* L. using single-factor experiments. To enhance extraction yield and biological activities, Response Surface Methodology (RSM) was employed to develop predictive models for simulating and optimizing the extraction process. The antiplasmodial activity of the extract was evaluated. Ethanol (EtOH), a hydroethanolic mixture of EtOH:H₂O (70:30), and distilled water were used as extraction solvents. Among the various extraction methods investigated, microwave-assisted extraction (MAE) with a hydroethanolic solvent provided the highest extraction yield (13.35 %) and the best IC₅₀ value of the *in vitro* antiplasmodial assay (2.67 µg/mL). Biological analyses confirmed that the extract exhibited strong antiplasmodial activity against *Plasmodium falciparum* strains *in vitro*. Under optimal microwave-assisted extraction conditions of 120 s for extraction time (X₁), 80 % (v/v) for ethanol concentration (X₂) and a solid-to-liquid ratio of 3.3:20 g/mL (X₃); the extraction yield reached 13.35%, closely aligning with the model's predicted value. This research work is of great significance as it has the propensity of contributing significantly to the management of malaria cases with attendant reduction in infant mortality rate in particular and general upgrading of healthcare in Africa.

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GRAPHICAL ABSTRACT:

Keywords: *Artemisia annua*, Microwave-assisted extraction, Antiplasmodial, Response Surface Methodology, bioactive molecules.

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INTRODUCTION

The *Artemisia* genus, belonging to the Asteraceae family, comprises a diverse group of plants that produce a lot of bioactive secondary metabolites widely used in traditional medicine. This genus includes approximately 344 species and 69 genera worldwide [1]. The species studied in this work is *Artemisia annua* L., commonly known as sweet wormwood, sweet annie, annual wormwood, or qinghao in Chinese [2]. *A. annua* is a significant source of approximately 600 secondary metabolites, such as terpenoids, polyphenols, coumarins, flavonoids, and essential oils [3]. These bioactive compounds, widely utilized in folk medicine, exhibit a broad spectrum of bioactivities, including antimalarial, antibacterial, and health-beneficial properties against diseases such as hepatitis, cancer, inflammation, infections, and others [4-6]. In modern applications, *A. annua* is used in medicine, agriculture, pharmaceuticals, and food industries, yet many of its active constituents remain underexplored. Following the isolation of artemisinin, a well-known antimalarial compound, extensive research on *A. annua* has led to the identification of nearly 600 secondary metabolites in recent decades [7]. The emergence of resistance to all current malaria drugs, including artemisinin, has increased the use of *A. annua*, particularly in regions with high malaria endemicity [9]. According to the World Health Organization (WHO), an estimated 2.2 billion malaria cases and 12.7 million deaths have been averted since 2000 [42]. However, malaria remains a significant global health threat, particularly in the WHO African Region, with approximately 263 million cases and 597,000 deaths reported in 2023. This represents about 11 million more cases than in 2022, with nearly unchanged mortality rates [8]. Combating this life-threatening disease is a key objective of the WHO's Global Technical Strategy, which aims to reduce malaria transmission and achieve a malaria-free world by 2030 [9]. Currently, artemisinin and its derivatives such as dihydroartemisinin, artesunate, artemether, and arteether are critical components of artemisinin-based combination therapies (ACTs) used in sub-Saharan Africa, where resistance in *Plasmodium falciparum* strains persists [10]. For plant-based combination therapies, *A. annua* should be harvested during the floral budding stage to maximize artemisinin content alongside other important bioactive compounds for treating malaria and other aforementioned diseases. One proposed alternative is the use of herbal teas prepared by aqueous infusion of *A. annua*'s aerial parts, which have shown promising results in cases of ACT resistance [11,12]. However, artemisinin, the primary antimalarial compound, has low water solubility, leading to treatment relapses and an increased risk of resistance. Recent studies suggest that therapeutic effects may result from the synergistic interactions of multiple secondary metabolites. For instance, Xiao *et al.* (2021) used various chromatographic methods to isolate and purify 15 compounds from the aqueous fraction of *A. annua*'s aerial parts, identifying them based on physicochemical properties and NMR spectral data [13,43]. Similarly, Wang *et al.* (2017) employed chromatography with a silica gel matrix and HPLC to purify 17 compounds from the ethyl acetate fraction of an ethanolic extract of *A. annua* [14,43]. Zhong *et al.* (2016) isolated six flavonoids from the plant. Despite extensive research on *A. annua*, the development of extracts with high bioactive secondary metabolite content for treating various diseases remains underexplored [15]. The low artemisinin content (0.5–0.8%) in *A. annua* and the complexity of its metabolic pathways, which are not fully elucidated, pose challenges to identifying potential therapies. This has prompted researchers to investigate the synergistic effects of secondary metabolites. Optimizing extraction techniques is crucial to maximizing the yield of active compounds. Conventional extraction methods, which involve immersing plant material in a solvent, have significant drawbacks, including low extract recovery, prolonged heating times that risk degrading bioactive metabolites, and high energy consumption due to intensive mixing, without effectively disrupting the plant matrix's cell structure. To address these issues, researchers have developed environmentally friendly extraction techniques using green solvents. These innovative eco-extraction methods include microwave-assisted extraction, ultrasound, flash release, supercritical fluid extraction, subcritical water extraction, and pulsed electric fields. These techniques improve extraction yield and purity while ensuring the safety and quality of the extracts. Microwave-assisted extraction (MAE) is a particularly effective method for extracting valuable compounds from plants [16-18]. MAE generates heat directly within the plant matrix by altering polarization through the motion of electric charges, causing cell rupture and releasing bioactive secondary metabolites. This approach aligns with 21st-century goals of protecting the environment and consumers while fostering ecological, economic, and innovative

advancements in academia and industry [19]. Despite extensive studies on *A. annua*, no research has utilized the central composite design through Response Surface Methodology (RSM) to optimize extraction conditions for obtaining extracts with high levels of active ingredients from *A. annua* of Adamawa region. Therefore, the primary objective of this research is to apply RSM to optimize microwave-assisted extraction conditions for *A. annua* to produce an extract with maximum antiparasitic activity and optimal bioactive compound content.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Plant Material and Chemicals

The plant material consisted of the whole plant of *Artemisia annua*, harvested in December 2024 in the Adamaoua region of Cameroon. The samples were then cut, dried for ten days at room temperature, and ground to fine powders using a mechanical grinder. A rotary evaporator was used to concentrate the different extracts at 40°C, varying the pressure according to the solvent to be evaporated (175 mbar, 337mbar, from 175mbar to 72 mbar respectively for ethanolic and hydroethanolic extract). The aqueous extracts were dried at room temperature using a freezer dryer (WK-12N, ZhengZhou Experimental Instrument Co., Ltd., Beijing, China).

All analytical grade solvents came from the Sigma Chemical Co. (St. Louis, MO, USA), and distilled water was obtained from the laboratory. The spectrophotometer Metertech Spectrophotometer UV/vis sp 8001, the rotary evaporator system (Büchi, Switzerland), and a microwave (FCMCR-3C-W) were also used.

Extraction Methods and Determination of Extraction Yield

For the extraction methods, two alternative and one conventional extraction techniques were used to determine the best extraction method and the best extraction yields for bioactive secondary metabolites. The three methods are described below, and all dried extracts obtained from each extraction technique were labelled and stored at 4°C for further investigations.

Microwave-Assisted Extraction (MAE)

Microwave-assisted extraction (MAE) leverages the heating effect of microwaves to facilitate the release of secondary metabolites from plant cells. The heat causes moisture within the cells to evaporate, generating steam that swells and ruptures the cells, thereby releasing their secondary metabolites. In addition to the dipole properties of plant cell components, the dipole rotation of solvent molecules under rapidly alternating electric fields plays a critical role in MAE. During microwave irradiation, the electric field oscillates 4.9×10^4 times per second, inducing solvent molecules to align with the field's normal phase. At such high frequencies, the solvent molecules cannot realign quickly enough, leading to vibration and heating of the plant matrix due to frictional forces [20]. In this study, MAE was performed using a microwave system (FCMCR-3C-W, Gongyi City Kerui Instrument Co., Ltd.) (Fig. 1). Dried *Artemisia annua* powder (20 g) was mixed with 200 mL of 70% aqueous ethanol in a glass conical flask and irradiated at 600 W for 90 s. Aqueous ethanol was selected as a safe and efficient solvent. After irradiation, the mixture was cooled for 1 min at 25°C and filtered using a Büchner funnel lined with Whatman No. 1 filter paper to obtain the dried extract [21]

Ultrasonic-Assisted Extraction procedure (UAE)

The ultrasound-assisted extraction (UAE) was performed using an ultrasonic apparatus (Clifton Range Ultrasonic Bath, SW Series of Industrial Ultrasonic Baths, compliant with EMC Directive 2014/30/EU, BS24 9BL, United Kingdom) operating at a fixed frequency of 38 kHz. Twenty grams (20 g) of dried *Artemisia annua* powder was placed in a conical flask containing 200 mL of ethanol, hydroethanolic solvent (70:30) and distilled water successively and immersed in the ultrasonic bath at 60°C for 1 h. The resulting plant extracts were filtered and dried at 40°C using a rotary evaporator (Heidolph, Germany) under reduced pressure to obtain an ethanol-free extract. The aqueous filtrate was lyophilized using a freezer dryer (WK-12N, ZhengZhou Experimental Instrument Co., Ltd., Beijing, China) [22,44].

Figure 1. Microwave Chemical Reactor FCMCR-3C-W (Gongyi City Kerui Instrument Co., Ltd)

Figure 2. The CliftonRange Ultrasonic bath

Maceration

In a flask, twenty grams of *A. annua* dried powder were soaked in 200 mL of different solvents precisely ethanol, hydroethanolic solvent (70:30) and distilled water successively. The conical flask was capped and shaken for 30 min before incubation for 24 h. After extraction, and vacuum filtration occur and the filtrate were concentrated at 40°C to obtained different extracts. Organic solvents were then removed by evaporation under reduced pressure with a Heidolph Germany rotary evaporator. For aqueous extracts, a freeze-dryer (WK-12N, ZhengZhou) at 20°C was used.

Figure 3. Freezer Dryer for Aqueous Extracts

For those extraction methods used, the extraction yield, was calculated as a percentage of the dry weight of the sample taken as follows:

$$Y\% = \frac{m_1}{m_o} \times \frac{100}{1} \quad (1)$$

Where m_o (g) and m_1 (g) are the weight of dry powder of *A. annua* and m_1 the dried extract weight, and Y is the extraction yield. These extraction methods were performed as in the previous work of Nana in (2024) [23].

Investigation of the Antiplasmodial Activity of Different Extracts

Extracts were screened *in vitro* against chloroquine-sensitive (*Pf3D7*) and multi-drug resistant (*PfDd2*) strains of *Plasmodium falciparum* using the DNA proliferation method based on SYBR Green. The antiplasmodial activity of the extracts was evaluated in 96-well flat-bottom microplates following the protocol described by Smilkstein *et al*, based on the ability of parasites to proliferate and survive in the presence of defined concentrations of the extract or reference molecule [24,45]. Parasite growth was assessed using SYBR Green I (Sigma-Aldrich), which binds to double-stranded DNA, producing fluorescence proportional to the number of parasites in the medium [45]. Experimentally, 90 μL of a ring-synchronized parasite suspension, prepared at 2% parasitemia and 1% hematocrit, was incubated with 10 μL of extracts or fractions at various pre-diluted concentrations [45]. The positive control consisted of reference molecules (artemisinin and chloroquine), while the negative control (100% growth) comprised 100 μL of the parasite suspension alone [45]. Plates were incubated for 72 hours at 37°C in a humidified incubator with 5% CO_2 . Final concentrations in the test plates ranged from 100 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ to 0.00016 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ ($\text{DMSO} \leq 0.1\%$) for extracts and from 1 μM to 0.0016 μM for artemisinin and chloroquine in a final volume of 100 μL . After incubation, 100 μL of SYBR Green I lysis buffer (0.2 μL SYBR Green I/mL lysis buffer), containing Tris (20 mM, pH 7.5), EDTA (5 mM), saponin (0.008% w/v), and Triton X-100 (0.08% v/v), was gently added to each well [45]. The plates were incubated for an additional hour in the dark [24]. Fluorescence was measured using a microplate reader (Infinite M200, Tecan) at excitation and emission wavelengths of 485 nm and 538 nm, respectively. Tests were performed in triplicate. The fluorescence values were used to calculate inhibition percentages (%INH) using Microsoft Excel [45], according to the formula:

$$\%Inhibition = \left[\frac{Negative\ control - Test}{Negative\ control} \right] \times \frac{100}{1} \quad (2)$$

Using GraphPad Prism software (version 5), median inhibitory concentrations (IC_{50}) were determined from sigmoidal concentration-response curves by plotting the percentage of inhibition against the decimal logarithm of the inhibitor concentration [45]. The percentage inhibition was also calculated using the formula:

$$\%Inhibition = \left[\frac{NPB - NPE}{NPB} \right] \times \frac{100}{1} \quad (3)$$

where NPE represents the number of schizonts per 200 erythrocytes counted for the extract at the tested concentration, and NPB represents the number of schizonts per 200 erythrocytes counted for the negative control. The IC_{50} , defined as the concentration of the extract exhibiting 50 % inhibitory activity, was determined using GraphPad Prism version 5 following the procedure of Smilkstein *et al.*, [24].

Optimization of the best extraction technique

Among the extraction techniques described above, microwave-assisted extraction (MAE) was selected for further optimization process with irradiation time (s), ethanol concentration (% v/v), and solid-to-liquid ratio (g/mL) as independent variables

Experimental and Central Composite Design

Response surface methodology (RSM) is a combination of mathematical and statistical techniques used for process optimization. Commonly used RSM designs include the central composite design (CCD). In this study, three main factors were selected as independent variables (table. 1), with the extraction yield as the response variable (Table 1). Prior to the optimization procedure, microwave-assisted extraction (MAE) was conducted at varying extraction times (s), ethanol concentrations (% v/v), and solid-to-liquid ratios (g/mL). A single-factor experimental design was used to identify the independent variables with the greatest impact on the extraction process, in the same approach a

study of one factor at time (OFAT) was operated in order to identify the lower and upper limits of the factors. Irradiation time (X_1), ethanol concentration (X_2), and solid-to-liquid ratio (X_3) were chosen as input variables. The coded levels and center point values for these three variables, as presented in table 1, were based on the results of the experimental domain investigation. The twenty trials listed in table 2 correspond to eight factorial points, six axial points at a distance of ± 1.68 from the center, and four replicates of the central point [46]. The experimental runs were randomized to minimize the effects of unexpected variability in the response variables.

Table 1. Response Surface Analysis Factors and Levels

Factors	Label	Units	Coded levels				
			$-\alpha$	-1	0	+1	$+\alpha$
Time	X_1	s	86.36	100	120	140	153.67
EtOH-H ₂ O Conc.	X_2	% (v/v)	63.18	70	80	90	96.82
Solid-to-liq ratio	X_3	g/mL	2.12/20	2.6/20	3.3/20	4/20	4.4/20

Table 2. Coded Values of the Different Independent Variables (X_1 , X_2 , and X_3)

Run	Coded values			Actual values			Response Y(%)
	X_1 (s)	X_2 (%)	X_3 (g/mL)	Time (s)	Conc (%)	Sol-to-liq ratio (g/mL)	
1	-1	-1	-1				
2	1	-1	-1				
3	-1	1	-1				
4	1	1	-1				
5	-1	-1	1				
6	1	-1	1				
7	-1	1	1				
8	1	1	1				
9	-1,682	0	0				
10	1,682	0	0				
11	0	-1,682	0				
12	0	1,682	0				
13	0	0	-1,682				
14	0	0	1,682				
15	0	0	0				
16	0	0	0				
17	0	0	0				
18	0	0	0				
19	0	0	0				
20	0	0	0				

Statistical Analysis

The regression equations were subjected to the Fisher test to determine the coefficient of determination R^2 [47]. The response surface methodology procedure of statistical analysis process and Design-Expert XIII software optimization toolbox were used to analyze the experimental data. With three factors at five levels, the generalized second-order polynomial model below was used to investigate linear, interaction and quadratic effects of different factors and optimal extraction conditions were estimated through regression analysis and three-dimensional (3D) response surface plots and contour plots of the three factors and dependent variable [48]. The model equation of response (Y) of three independent variables (X_1 , X_2 , and X_3 ,) is given in the following equation:

$$Y = \beta_0 + \sum_{i=1}^3 \beta_i X_i + \sum_{i=1}^3 \beta_{ii} X_i^2 + \sum_{i<j=1}^3 \beta_{ij} X_i X_j \quad (4)$$

Where Y is the predicted response or dependant variable; β_0 is a constant coefficient; β_i , β_{ii} and β_{ij} are the coefficients of the linear, quadratic and interactive terms, respectively; x_i and x_j represent the coded independent variables [49]. The response surface analysis and the software were used to

generate different graphs and contour plots. Optimum conditions of the independent variables were obtained and the agreement between the experimental data and the models were assessed by using Absolute Mean Deviation Analysis (AMDA) with its formula below:

$$AMDA = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^p \left| \frac{Y_{iexp} - Y_{ipred}}{Y_{iexp}} \right|}{p} \quad (5)$$

Where Y_{iexp} experimental value of total extraction yield, Y_{ipred} predicted value of total extraction yield and p the total of run. The test factors were coded according to the standard formula below:

$$X = \frac{(X_1 - X_0)}{\Delta X} \quad (6)$$

Where x was a coded value of the test variable; X_i was the corresponding actual value of variable; X_0 was the actual value of the X_i on the centre point; and ΔX was the step change value [50]. Checkpoint studies were conducted to validate the mathematical model generated during RSM implementation [51].

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Yields Estimation from the Different Extraction Methods and Antiplasmodial Assessment

Yields estimation from the different extraction methods

By comparing the different extraction methods, it is seen from fig. 4 that, the highest extraction yield was obtained by the MAE (09.02%). This is approximately two times higher than that obtained by the UAE (5.04%), three times higher than that obtained by the CSE (03.01% and 3.91%) for maceration and infusion respectively. During the microwave-assisted extraction process, microwave energy is used to heat solvent in contact with plant matrix, thus facilitating the release of targeted compounds from the matrix into the solvent. As such, microwave deliver energy efficiently to materials through molecular interaction with the electromagnetic field as well as to offer a rapid transfer of energy to the extraction solvent and plant materials [25,52]. As in countless works, it has already been shown that alternative extraction methods give better extraction yields than conventional methods [23], [26], [27]. On the other hand, among the alternative methods, it turns out that MAE gives better results than UAE. These results are in conformity with previous studies which study in a comparative manner Microwave-Assisted Extraction and Ultrasound-Assisted Extraction Techniques (MAE vs. UAE). Optimized Production of Enriched Extracts in Phenolic Compounds of *Camellia japonica* showed that the maximum yields (80%) were obtained at high temperatures and short durations (180 °C, 5 min) when using MAE. Lower yields (56%) were obtained using UAE (optimal conditions 62% amplitude, 8 min, and 39% acidified ethanol) [28,53]. In the same vein, Thy Minh reveals in their work on the Recovery of Phenolic Compounds and Antioxidants from Coffee Pulp (*Coffea canephora*) Waste using Ultrasound and Microwave-Assisted Extraction that bioactive compounds and antioxidant capacity constituted around one half of MAE [29,53].

Table 3. Extraction Yield Extracts from *A. annua* L. for the Two Extraction Techniques and Different Extraction Solvents

	Methods used	Solvent used	Obtained mass	Ext. Yields
Advanced extraction technique	Microwave	EtOH	1.242	6.21
		EtOH/H ₂ O (70 :30)	1.804	09.02
		H ₂ O	0.890	4.45
	Ultrasonic	EtOH	0.888	4.44
		EtOH/H ₂ O (70 :30)	1.008	5.04

Conventional extraction technique	Infusion	H ₂ O	0.568	2.84
		EtOH/H ₂ O (70 :30)	0.602	3.01
	Maceration	H ₂ O	0.410	2.05
		EtOH	0.666	3.33
		EtOH/H ₂ O (70 :30)	0.782	3.91
		H ₂ O	0.340	1.70

Figure 4. Influence of the Extraction Methods with Hydroethanolic Solvent on Extraction Yields of *A. annua* L

The extraction method and the solvent used play a key role in the extraction of bioactive secondary metabolites from plant material. The use of several extraction methods can provide more comprehensive information about the biological properties. Extraction methods can also provide sometimes their metabolic pathways, pharmacological mechanisms of action and relation structure-activity. Aqueous ethanol, a safe and effective solvent was used in the experiments because ethanol has a larger dissipation factor and a higher volatility than water and a high dielectric constant than pure ethanol, and a microwave frequency of 2450 MHz [54].

Antiplasmodial assessment

Antiplasmodial activity of the extracts from *A. annua* was assessed by method based on SYBR Green; Extracts were screened *in vitro* against chloroquine-sensitive (*Pf3D7*) and multi-drug resistant (*PfDd2*) strains of *Plasmodium falciparum* using the DNA proliferation method based on SYBR Green. The results of *in vitro* antiplasmodial activity on the chloroquine-sensitive PfNF54-E and multi-resistant PfDd2 strain are presented in the diagram below (Fig 5). In order to provide a basis for the analysis of the results of the interest extract of *Artemisia annua* L. according to the IC₅₀ value obtained, the classification criteria established by Kumari (2016) were used [30]: The analysis of these results shows the hydroethanolic extract obtained by MAE is biologically very active. This result is justified because the active principle responsible for the antiplasmodial activity of the plant is artemisinin. And according to the work of Misra on the quantification of Artemisinin from *Artemisia annua*, Artemisinin content was found to be present in a decreasing order of artemisinin: leaves > side branches > main stem [55]. However, no artemisinin was detected in root extract or artemisinin may be below the detection limit in root extract of *A. annua* [27] (Misra *et al.*, 2014). This strong antiplasmodial activity recorded in the hydroethanolic extracts could be explained by the high solubility of artemisinin (active principle of the plant) in the ethanol/water mixture. Our results corroborate with those of Gbaguidi *et al.* (2015) [31] who confirmed antiplasmodial activity in hydroethanolic extracts. Similarly, as for the extraction yields, each *A. annua* extract has different degrees of inhibition effects; amongst the four extraction methods, MAE shows the least value in terms of inhibitory concentration meaning that a small amount or concentration of the extract (2.67 µg/mL) can inhibit the proliferation of plasmodium parasites by 50 % thus indicates a more potent antiplasmodial effect.

Figure 5. IC⁵⁰ Antiplasmodial Values of *Artemisia annua* L. Extracts

Ranges for Relevant Parameters for Efficiency and Yield Enhancement in MAE

A preliminary study consisting of single factor design was previously conducted which allowed us to determine three influential factors on the microwave-assisted extraction of *A. annua*. Thus, the extraction time, the concentration of the solvent and the solid-to-liquid ratio were studied using a face-center composite plane. This study allowed us to research the experimental domain of the different independent variables to be used in response surface methodology.

Effect of extraction time (X₁) on MAE yield

Extraction time is one of the advantages of microwave-assisted extraction because it is generally short, from a few seconds to several minutes. In this study, the different time points investigated were (20, 40, 60, 80, 100, 120 and 140) s, with the two other parameters being kept constant: liquid-to-solid ratio was 1:20, and ethanol concentration was 70%. The effect of microwave irradiation time on the extraction yield is illustrated in Fig. 6.

Figure 6. The Effect of Microwave Irradiation Time in Single-Factor Experiments

In view of its results, a significant increase in the extraction yield was observed with prolonging the irradiation time from 20 to 100 s with a peak yield of 9.01% at 120 s and after that, a reducing trend from 120 to 140 s was observed [56]. Despite the risk of secondary metabolites degradation with a prolonged microwave irradiation time, with a reasonable time, MAE easily disrupt the plant's cell wall and release the biomolecules [32]. Therefore, 120 s was selected as the optimum extraction time for subsequent experiments. For further investigations, the microwave irradiation time range of 100-140 s was selected to be applied in the RSM runs application [56]. It is noted that after 120 s, increasing the extraction duration up to 140 s does not significantly ($P>0.05$) improve the extraction of biomolecules. This observation could be explained by Fick's second law of diffusion which stipulated that, after the equilibrium between the concentration of the solute of the solid matrix and the solvent after a certain time, excessive extraction time is no longer necessary to extract the active compounds [33].

Effect of ethanol concentration (X_2) on MAE yield

For a good solubility process, microwave-assisted extraction as other techniques extractions, the choice of solvent is determined by the solubility of the molecules of interest and by the solvent-matrix interactions [49]. However, in MAE exclusively, the choice of the solvent is mainly linked to its ability to absorb microwaves because to obtain an optimal extraction process, the extraction solvent must have a high dielectric constant in order to have a low dissipation factor, hence the need to mix water with a dielectric constant of 78.3 with ethanol with a constant of 24 at a certain concentration. Thus the concentrations investigated are 20 %, 40 %, 60 %, 70 %, 80 %; and 100 %. The other parameters being kept constant (Nana, 2016). The extraction yield increases with the ethanol concentration then drops after a maximum around 80%. But the yield declined to 1.45 % the ethanol concentration gradually increases to 80 %. It is because the higher concentration of ethanol blocks secondary metabolites diffusion from vegetal matrix [57]. All the results of the different concentration are recorded in figure 7 below.

Figure 7. Effect of Ethanol Concentration in Single-Factor Experiments

Effect of solid-to-liquid ratio (X_3) on MAE yield

The solid-to-liquid ratio is decisive for the success of a good microwave-assisted extraction. Therefore, the volume of solvent must be sufficient for the matrix to remain immersed during the entire extraction. Thus, the microwaves will allow the heating of the solvent and the latter, by conduction, will heat the plant material. The volume of the solvent should be large enough so that the plant material remains submerged during the entire extraction [32]. Then, this effect was investigated and the results are depicted in Fig. 8. The ratios investigated was set at (1/20; 2/20; 3/20; 4/20, 5/20, and 6/20) g/mL, (w/v). Meanwhile, the other independent variables were fixed: the concentration of ethanol was 70 %, and the time of extraction was 30 min [33], [34]. It was shown

that the extraction yield was increased from 2.50 % to 7.00 % as the solid-to-liquid ratio increased from 2,6:20 to 4:20 (g/mL) (w/v) and this domain was choose for the best conditions for RSM studies.

Figure 8. Effect of Solid-to-Liquid Ratio (X3) in Single-Factor Experiments

Experimental Design for Optimization of the Process

Response Surface Methodology (RSM) as an optimization method was employed to determine the optimum conditions for the maximum recovery yield of secondary metabolites from *A. annua* using Central Composite Design (CCD). Accordingly, a centered composite design (CCD) of twenty experiments was carried out under the influence of irradiation time (X_1), ethanol concentration (X_2) and solid-to-liquid ratio (X_3) in order to improve the extraction yield. The results exhibited in table 3 below indicates the results of the uncoded values of independent variables, their optimal levels and interactions for each experiment. The values of extraction yields varied from (9.818 to 13.357) %. Twenty experimental runs (in triplicates) were carried out.

Table 4. Central Composite Design with Uncoded Independent Variables and Responses

Run	Uncoded values of factors			Predicted response value	Experimental response value
	X_1 (s)	X_2 (%)	X_3 (g/mL)		
				$Y_{Pred.}$ (%)	$Y_{Exp.}$ (%)
1	100	70	2.6/20	11.954	12.22
2	140	70	2.6/20	10.385	10.4346
3	100	90	2.6/20	10.939	11.0171
4	140	90	2.6/20	10.725	10.6631
5	100	70	4/20	9.818	9.75728
6	140	70	4/20	12.925	12.6467
7	100	90	4/20	11.818	11.933
8	140	90	4/20	11.746	11.8642
9	86.364	80	3.3/20	12.949	12.6372
10	153.636	80	3.3/20	11.864	11.7664
11	120	63.182	3.3/20	11.599	11.9282
12	120	96.8179	3.3/20	11.823	11.9036
13	120	80	2.123/20	10.725	10.5945
14	120	80	4.4/20	10.925	10.8321
15	120	80	3.3/20	13.636	13.3478
16	120	80	3.3/20	12.727	13.3478
17	120	80	3.3/20	13.757	13.3478
18	120	80	3.3/20	13.576	13.3478
19	120	80	3.3/20	13.182	13.3478
20	120	80	3.3/20	13.212	13.3478

Note: X_1 : Irradiation time (s), X_2 : Ethanol concentration (%), X_3 : solid-to-liquid ratio (g/mL) and Y (%): Extraction yields. It is observed from the table 3 above that there is no significant difference at the 5 % threshold between the experimental and the predicted responses. The maximum extraction yield value of 13, 35 % was achieved at the conditions of run number 17, with irradiation time of 120 s, ethanol concentration of 80 % and solid-to-liquid ratio of 3.3/20 g/ml

Fitting the Model and Analysis of Variance

The significance and adequacy of the models are assessed using analysis of variance (ANOVA) and the results summed in table 3. According to the variance analysis of the regression model, a p-value less than 0.05 ($p < 0.05$) indicates the significance at the 95% confidence level and a p-value less than 0.0001 ($p < 0.0001$) indicates the high significance of the regression model terms [56]. Moreover, p-values greater than 0.10 indicate that the model terms are insignificant. Likewise, R-squared values of the model is above 95.6 %, indicating that the predicted values correlate well with the experimental data meaning that the models are adequate and reliable. Response Surface Methodology was used to obtain the relationships between the extraction yield and the investigated factors. Multiple regression analysis was used to analyze the experimental data, and it was found that regression analysis of the extraction response was fitted using a second-order polynomial equation as expressed in the equation below

$$Y = -104,764 + 0,798683*X_1 + 194,524*X_3 - 0,00261684*X_1^2 - 0,0021825*X_1*X_2 - 0,00529672*X_2^2 - 1,445*X_2X_3 - 307,411*X_3^2 \quad (7)$$

Where (X_1 , X_2 and X_3) are respectively the irradiation time (s) of extraction, the ethanol concentration (%) and the solid-to-liquid ratio (g/mL). ANOVA was used for the statistical significance impact of the factors and the interactions amongst them. It's emerging from table 3 that seven effects significantly influence at the 5 % threshold. According to the p and F-values the factors with the largest effect on extraction yield (Y) efficiency are, from greatest to least effects the quadratic effect of time X_1^2 , the quadratic effect of ethanol concentration X_2^2 , followed by the effect of the interaction of ethanol concentration-solid-liquid ratio X_2X_3 , the quadratic effect of solid-to-liquid ratio X_3^2 , the linear effect of irradiation time X_1 and the linear effect of liquid-to-solid ratio. However, the linear effect of ethanol concentration and the interaction irradiation time-solid-liquid ratio X_1X_3 did not show any significant effect. The analysis of variance of the regression of the coefficients consists of analyzing the impact of the variables (X_1 , X_2 and X_3) at $p < 0,05$ in order to see the degree of influence of the independent variable on the MAE of *A. annua*.

Table 5. Analysis of Variance for the Fitted Quadratic Polynomial Model and Regression Coefficient Estimation

Factors	Sum of squares	DF	Mean squares	F-value	P-value
X_1	1.916	1	1.916	16.34	0.002**
X_2	0.0335245	1	0.0335245	0.29	0.604
X_3	0.606679	1	0.606679	5.17	0.046*
X_1^2	15.79	1	15.79	134.64	0.000***
X_1X_2	1.52426	1	1.52426	13.00	0.004**
X_1X_3	0.0741125	1	0.0741125	0.63	0.445
X_2^2	4.04311	1	4.04311	34.48	0.0002***
X_2X_3	2.04626	1	2.04626	17.45	0.0019**
X_3^2	2.04372	1	2.04372	17.43	0.0019**
Total error	1.17275	10	0.117275		
Total (corr.)	26.6064	19			

Note: *Significant ($0.05 > P \geq 0.01$); **very significant ($0.01 > P \geq 0.001$); ***highly significant ($P \leq 0.001$); Sum of the squared: Differences between the average values and the overall mean; Degrees of freedom (DF); Sum of squares divided by DF; F-value: Test for comparing term variance with residual variance; P-value: Probability of seeing the observed F-value if the null hypothesis is true.

According to the validation indicators, like improved R^2 , and AADM, the model obtained was validated. While knowing that Joglekar and May (1987) consider a model valid if the model explains at least 80% of the variability of the response more precisely the square of the adjusted coefficient of determination R^2 [35]. In the present study, the value of R^2 is 0.96, which means that only 0.44 of the variations are not explained by the model. In addition, the value of the coefficient of determination

is (R^2 adjusted to 0.92), which confirms the significance of the model. The adjusted R^2 value after eliminating unnecessary coefficients from the model) will be much lower than that of R^2 if the model contains many unnecessary (non-significant) terms. Other authors, Dalgaard and Jorgensen (1998) estimate a valid model if the accuracy and bias factor is between 0.75 and 1.2 Baş and Boyac (2007), our study gave values 1.002088; 1.00933 and 1.002088 respectively; judge a model to be valid if the AADM is between 0 and 0.3; in our case AADM is 0.0002 [36], [37], [38]. Under these standard criteria, our results is in accordance with them and the experimental data is reliable, thus the validation of the model.

Table 6. Regression Coefficients and Analysis of the Variance (ANOVA) for the Experimental Results

Validation indicators	Y (%)	Standard value
R^2 (%)	95.6	100
R^2 adjusted (%)	91.6	100
AMDA	0.0002	0 -0.3
Biais factor	1.002088	1
AccuracyFactors (Af_1)	1.002088	1
Accuracy Factors (Af_2)	1.00933	1

Note: AMDA: Absolute Mean Deviation Analysis

Analysis of Percentage of Factor's Contributions Diagram

The linear, the cumulative and the quadratic effects of the independent variables on the extraction yield are shown in fig. 9.

Figure 9. Contribution Percentage of Independent Variables on Hydroethanolic MAE of Secondary Metabolites from *Artemisia annua*

It arises from the fig. 9 that the linear effects of solid-to-liquid ratio (X_3) contribute to increase the extraction of secondary metabolites from *A. annua*. The liq-to-solid ratio factor highlights the appropriate amount of plant material to dissolve in a solvent to achieve a good concentration gradient in the solution and effective convection, enabling ideal material transfer [39]. Nevertheless, with an excessive diffusion (X_3^2), a significant drop is observed by the negative effect of quadratic effect of solid-to-liquid ratio. The figure also presents a low contribution of linear effect of irradiation time as well as its quadratic effect (0.16 and -0.0052%) on the hydroethanolic microwave assisted extraction [58]. This low rate of mass transfer due to the low diffusion can be due to the high viscosity of the reaction medium at the beginning of the transfer process. Thus the needing of an adequate time for

the different secondary metabolites to be dissolved from the plants matrix into the solution. These results are similar to the research work of Tsatsop *et al.* on the Sequential extraction of quercetin-3-O-rhamnoside from *Piliostigma thonningii* Schum leaves using microwave technology [40, 58].

Graphical Response Surface Analysis

Response surfaces are three-dimensional graphs where the horizontal plane of the figure illustrates the range of variation of two factors and the vertical axis illustrates the variation of the response from the model. In this study, the response surface and contour plots are constructed according to the fitted models. Figs. 10 present the plots with one variable kept at medium level and the other two within the tested range [59].

Figure 10. Three-Dimensional Surface Plot of Interactive Effects of Three Independent Variables on Extraction Yields

As exhibited in fig 10 A, the interaction between irradiation time and ethanol concentration on the extraction yield of secondary metabolites from *A. annua* increases over time up to 126 s and ethanol concentration of 83%. These interactions enhanced the extraction yields. For bioactive molecules to be released into the extraction medium, it takes a minimum amount of time for the hydroethanolic solvent to penetrate the powder of the plant sample, dissolve these active substances which then diffuse from plant cell to extraction solvent. The extraction time, which is of the order of seconds indicates that the extraction of the compounds could be facilitated by microwaves. Thus, prolonged exposure leads to destruction of thermosensitive molecules; corresponding to the negative influence of the quadratic effect of time observed on the extraction of bioactive molecules [58]. These results are in agreement with those of Nana (2016). Fig. 10 B presents the response surface and contour plots for extraction yields under ethanol concentration X_2 and solid-to-liquid ratio X_3 . The cumulative

influences of the two factors exert highly significant effects on extraction yields ($p < 0.01$). According to the contour plot, when X_2 and X_3 increase, the yield increases but, after the optimum value of 12 % extraction yield begins to decrease at about 85 % ethanol [60]. At X_2 below 80 %, the yield rises following an increase of X_3 from 2.6/20 to 4.4/20. Such values indicate that the hydroethanolic solvent has provided sufficient microwave heat to the plant cell, and thus increasing the volume of solvent promoted the diffusion of the secondary metabolites. However, at X_2 above 85 %, the yield decreases with X_3 rising from 2.6/20 to 4.4/20 [60]. These findings indicate that the highest extraction yield could be achieved when using 3.3/20 g/mL and ethanol concentration at 80 %. One of the explanations could be that, as ethanol concentration increases, the polarity of solvent changes, which would extract more bioactive compounds [60]. More, the aqueous solvent could facilitate an increase in the extraction yields since water could be helpful to improve swelling of sample, which is favorable to increase the contact surface area between the plant matrix and the solvent, resulting in increase of the extraction yield [41, 60]. Based on the established mathematical model, the optimal experimental conditions were, irradiation time of 120 s, the solvent concentration of 80 % and the solid-to-liquid ratio of 3,3/20 (g/mL).

CONCLUSION

Extraction yield of bioactive secondary metabolites, antiplasmodial assessment and optimization of the best extraction technique were the main research question addressed in this work. Following the different investigations above, MAE appears to be the best extraction approach. As such, an optimized microwave-assisted extraction method of secondary metabolites from *A. annua* has been developed. Our results suggested that MAE can be an efficient technique for polyphenolics extraction. With short extraction time, the suitable concentration of ethanol and an adequate liquid to solid ratio, a bioactive extract with high extraction yields and great antiplasmodial potential can be obtained. The central composite design used single factor experiments was accomplished for the optimization of the MAE process. As the results, optimal conditions for maximizing the total extraction yields of 13.35 % are determined to be: The irradiation time of 120 s, the solvent concentration of 80 % and the liquid-to-solid ratio of 3,3/20 (mL/g). The verification results and validation parameters showed that, on the one hand, with an R^2 of 95.6 % and R^2 adjusted of 91.6 %, and with AMDA (Absolute Mean Deviation Analysis) of 0.0002, the developed model was suitable and reliable for describing the effects and relationship of the MAE factors on the bioactive secondary metabolites yield, on the other hand, RSM could be successfully applied for optimizing the extraction processes. Thus, MAE could be applied to obtain an extract with a rich artemisinin content with an IC_{50} value of 2.67 μ g/ml. Therefore, this study underlines that MAE is an environmental friendly extraction method that can be used to recover from *Artemisia annua* L. under optimal conditions, extracts with antiplasmodial potential. This may be the first report on the extraction of secondary metabolites from *A. annua* from Adamawa region in Cameroon using MAE.

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COMPETING INTERESTS

Authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

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